

**Understanding People with Disabilities
within the Biblical Concepts of *Imago Dei* and *Imitatio Christi***

Guo-Hui Xie*^{1,2}, EdD, BCET, BCSE

Special Education Consultant
Steadfastness Training Consultancy, Singapore

Abstract: This paper is divided into two parts. In Part I on The Disability History and Models of People with Disabilities (PWDs), it examines briefly two important aspects in understanding PWDs: (1) the disability history from the British perspective from the Medieval Era through the times of Renaissance and Colonialization, First and Second World Wars to the present millennium; and (2) the selected five models of PWDs, i.e., the Religious, Medical, Social, Rights-based, and Media models. In Part II on The Biblical Perspective on Disability and PWDs, it examines the concept of PWDs from two key concepts: (1) *Imago Dei*, which comes from the Latin Bible, translated to English as “image of God”; and (2) *Imitatio Christi*, in Latin, which means “imitation of Christ”, written by Thomas à Kempis (b.1380AD-d.1471AD) – also known as Thomas of Kempen – was a German-Dutch canon regular in the Roman Catholic Church during the late medieval era. The aim of this short paper is to provide a better understanding of people with disabilities from the biblical viewpoint.

Key Words: Biblical Perspective, Disability, Imago Dei, Imitatio Christi, People with Disabilities

***Corresponding author:** Dr Guo-Hui Xie

E-Mail: xguohui62@gmail.com

1. Introduction

If all people with disabilities (PWDs in short) are recognized as a minority in a general population, they are very likely to constitute the largest minority group, for instance, in the United States. Many of them have also contributed and continue to do so in enriching the history of mankind despite their special needs. Though they have always been neglected in the past and more so now during the Covid-19 pandemic, their constant cries for their diverse voices be heard, their frequent continuous struggles to be taken notice and their issues of concern to be addressed appropriately, their collective needs of well-being and belongingness to local and global communities to be acknowledged and be provided for like any typical person ... all these should not be dismissed.

“Because the history of disability is the history of people, it is layered with objects, innovation, struggle, emotion, drama, and surprise” (Behring Center, National Museum of American History, 2015, para.1). The PWDs have not always been treated fairly or taken seriously. Since

¹ The author is an ordained minister by the Christian Open Ministry in his outreach to people with disabilities.

² He is also a visiting professor at the Universidade de São José in Macau, PRC.

the 1900s, there was a drastic transformation in terms of treatment and perceptions of disability largely because these PWDs began demanding and pushing for those changes, e.g., the disability rights movement in the 1960s and 1970s, which is just like other civil rights movements, with its long history (for more information on the history of disability rights movement in other countries besides the US and UK, see <https://findhistoryhere.com/history-of-disability-rights-movement>).

During the 1930s, prior to the Second World War, the PWDs were often seen as people who were defective and unhealthy, and their families abandoned on the streets and left them to thrive on their own. This is most likely the result of a lack of understanding about disabilities and the sequelae of such diverse conditions. More shocking is when a Nobel Prize winner, Dr Alexis Carrel (1939; see Clapton & Fitzgerald, 2005, for more detail), at the Rockefeller Institute published his book “Man the Unknown” (Carrel, 1939), suggesting that people who were mentally ill could be removed with suitable gases at small euthanasia institutions. Indeed, in that same year, amid the World War II, Adolf Hitler (b.1889-d.1945), a German politician and leader of the Nazi Party, who rose to power to become chancellor on January 30, 1933, ordered a wide spread mercy-killing of people who were sick and/or disabled. This event was known as the Nazi Euthanasia Program (code-named Aktion T4) and its aim was to eliminate all those people, including children and youth, whose life was considered unworthy of living. For instance, in 1940, Adolf Hitler gave an order to transfer 908 patients from Schoenbrunn (an institution for chronically ill and intellectually challenged people) to a euthanasia instillation at Eglfing-Haar to be gassed. By 1941, after over a hundred thousand of such people lost their lives unnecessarily to being gassed, Aktion T4 was temporarily suspended. However, the program resumed again with a different approach – this time without the use of gassing – and instead, PWDs were left to die by starvation or being used for medical experiments and military training practice (e.g., target shooting).

With the end of the Second World War, there was a wide range of issues concerning injuries and disabilities to be addressed by various governments in different parts of the world. For instance, the American soldiers returning from war were financially compensated by the US Government as well as being provided vocational rehabilitation. As a result, during the period of 1940-1950, there were several government-funded and charity-based welfare organizations set up to provide rehabilitation rather than institutionalization for these PWDs. More research studies were carried out to inform the general public about the correct types of treatments for different kinds of disabilities.

During the 1950s, PWDs were often admitted – against their own free will – to institutions by families. One common reason or explanation that is often cited is that these PWDs were seen as a burden. As a PWD, the individual was treated as a patient, who could not contest the confinement within the institution (or institutionalization). Many of them often suffered abuse and neglect in silence, with poor or only substantial health and low safety conditions, deprivation of their rights to be treated equal like fellow human beings, given forms of electroshock therapy, painful restraints, negligent seclusion and experimental treatments, and also, at times, unnecessary and unproven procedures.

With the activists and advocates for the rights of PWDs on the move in the US as well as many other countries in the western Europe, governments from different countries all over the world met up to signed a convention on the rights of PWDs. In 1975, the UN Declaration on the Rights of Disabled People was passed and it “marked the beginning of a new conceptual approach to disability issues as human rights issues” (Brown, 2015, para.5). By 1996, other

legislations such as the Human Rights and Equal Opportunity Discrimination Act, the Disability Services Act, and the Disability Discrimination Act were also passed by the US Congress to provide for PWDs without prejudice. The National Disability Advisory Council (now known as the National Council on Disability) was established within the US Department of Education in 1978 as “an independent federal agency charged with advising the President, Congress, and other federal agencies regarding policies, programs, practices, and procedures that affect people with disabilities” (National Council on Disability, 1978/2020, para. 1-2).

PART I: Disability History and Models of People with Disabilities

In this first part of the paper, there are two important aspects to be discussed. First, the author has chosen to introduce the disability history from the British perspective since the United Kingdom by its traditions is a Christian nation, whose monarch is the supreme governor of the Church of England. It provides the Christian context upon which our understanding of disability history and PWDs will be based. Second, five models of PWDs, i.e., religious, medical, social, rights-based, and media, have been selected for a brief discussion in better understanding the disability and PWDs today.

2. A Brief History of People with Disabilities

Throughout history, the PWDs are often neglected by their own communities, hidden away from the public eye by their families and cursed by many religious or spiritual leaders, strangers and public in general. When they appeared in public or made visible, they are often the subjects (e.g., Joseph Merrick of the Elephant Man’s fame who became a travelling exhibit to earn a living; see Howell & Ford, 1980/1992, for a review) of exhibitions (e.g., as freaks at the Barnum and Bailey Circus between 1871 and 2017) and objects of ridicule. In most societies throughout the world, even today, the PWDs are dealt with by putting them in institutions, asylums or prisons, and as for women and girls with disabilities, it is an acceptable treatment to have them sterilized.

In this paper, the author has chosen to use the British disability history as a frame of reference to illustrate the changing landscape that has impacted the lives of PWDs almost close to a millennium. Readers can always choose to use the US historical development of PWDs or any others of their preference. Moving on, according to the Historic England (2020), “disabled people’s lives are integral to the heritage all around us. From leper chapels built in the 1100s to protests about accessibility in the 1980s, the built environment is inextricably linked to the stories of disabled people, hidden and well-known” (para.1). To understand the history of PWDs, this author has decided to take the readers on a brief journey through the English history in order to better understand the disability history. The Historic England (2020) has divided it into five periods (from the British perspective) and the author of this paper has termed each period as an era with a specific name for easy and quick cross-referencing in the discussion as follows:

2.1 First Disability Period: 1050-1485 AD (Medieval Era)

During the Medieval Era, the leper, the blind, the dumb, the deaf, the mentally impaired, the cripple, the incapacitate and the lunatic were the PWDs highly visible in daily living encounters. Born with a disability or caused by a disease (e.g., leprosy), the attitudes towards such people at that time were mixed. Many thought it was a punishment for sin as so believed in the Religious M-PWDs or for those who were superstitious thought such people were “born under the hostile influence of the planet Saturn” (Historic England, 2020, para. 3). There were also those who firmly believed that PWDs were closer to God because they were suffering purgatory on earth rather than after death and would get to heaven sooner. Many PWDs also

made pilgrimages to holy sites (e.g., the shrine of Thomas Becket in Canterbury) in search of a miraculous cure or relief.

At that time, no state provision for PWDs was available. Many of them continued to struggle with their daily living, and they had to live and work in their own communities. Their family members as well as friends also provided them with much needed support. For those who were unable to work, if they were fortunate enough, the folk in the town or village, where they lived, might support them, too. However, sometimes PWDs resorted to begging for money and food as their needs were not adequately met. In most cases, the Catholic monks and nuns, who sheltered pilgrims and strangers, also provided and cared for the PWDs as that was their Christian calling to show compassion and to serve.

Based on the teachings of the Roman Catholic Church in England (the Church of England was formed only after it separated from the Roman Catholic Church in 1534), caring for sick and disabled was considered a spiritual obligation. The Catholic monks and nuns would follow the seven so-called comfortable works: feeding, clothing and housing the poor, visiting them when in prison or sick, offering drink to the thirsty, and burial. The seven spiritual works also included counseling and comforting the sick.

It was also during this Medieval Era that religious establishments helped to set up a nationwide network of hospitals, e.g., specialized hospitals were created for different conditions such as leprosy, blindness and physical disability. Bedlam, the first mental institution in England, was originally known as Bethlehem Hospital built in the City of London. Almshouses were also founded to provide support and shelter for PWDs as well as the elderly infirm.

According to Historic England (2020), “[T]he people, religious institutions and towns and cities of the medieval period were pioneers in terms of providing a specialised response to disability” (para. 8). Today, only a few of these medieval buildings stand. However, this medieval approach to care for PWDs eventually developed into the modern system of public services that are provided for PWDs today.

2.2 Second Disability Period: 1485-1660 AD (Renaissance Era)

During this period, beginning with a 1531 law under King Henry VIII (and culminated over the years into a series of Poor Law Acts of 1834) introduced to mete out punitive measures aimed at able-bodied poor people deemed idle or unwilling to work. The legislation was also designed to define English society's obligations and duties to the destitute, aged, sick or disabled judged unable to look after themselves.

In 1534, the Church of England split from the Roman Catholic Church, after the English church renounced the papal authority. It was the result of King Henry VIII's failure to secure an annulment of his marriage to Queen Catherine of Aragon. The English King ordered the dissolution of the Catholic monasteries across the country. As such, religious houses were demolished with the Catholic monks and nuns being driven out. The hospitals in these religious establishments were also destroyed, along with the care service system that had been serving sick and disabled as well as the elderly infirm, and “poverty and a life on the streets followed this destruction” (Historic England, 2020, para. 2). Four years later, in 1538, a petition to King Henry VIII called for the re-foundation of the hospitals that had been shut down. However, very little was done over the next 30 years. The poor and needy, the sick and disabled, and the elderly infirm continued to struggle throughout their daily existence. The small Bethlehem Hospital was the only institution for mentally ill people to survive, and much later, the

Corporation of London took over the running of the hospital in 1547 and employed its first medically qualified superintendent.

During that era, life was tough for everyone and more so for the PWDs as well as those who were mentally ill living in their communities. They were treated with astrological, traditional, religious and psychological remedies, usually with no significant improvement. Providing and caring for the PWDs as well as the poor and needy and the elderly infirm soon became a civic duty, rather than a spiritual obligation or religious matter. Rich benefactors began to fund the buildings for the PWDs as well as to enhance their own reputation, rather than to save their souls as the Religious M-PWDs would have preferred. New hospitals were built and some old ones were re-founded, with many of them funded by parish collections, taxes and donations. “By the end of the 16th century, new almshouses hospitals were springing up” (Historic England, 2020, para. 5) everywhere, not only in London.

2.3 Third Disability Period: 1660-1832 AD (Colonialization Era)

The Colonialization Period (1660-1832) was the era when several European naval powers such as the Portuguese, the Dutch and the English were exploring the new world and beyond their respective shores to set up colonies in these foreign soils to establish their own empires and also to spread Christianity to the natives.

During that era, living with disability in England was better than the era before. With PWDs at all levels of society, ranging from the beggars on the street to distinguished artists, many generally lived in their own homes within their communities. They married as well as supported themselves if they could. There were also those PWDs who received financial help or other forms of support from the better-off. Moreover, people began to question or even challenge the idea that God could cause someone to become mad and disabled. No longer for a PWD who suffered a misfortune was seen as a divine punishment, but s/he deserved charity. Also, more people began to dismiss the idea that madness was a demonic possession of the soul. With better medico-psychological approach, madness was seen as a loss of reason and that it could be restored if treated appropriately.

After the Great Fire of London in 1666, wealthy businessmen established a massive building program that included grand new hospitals. The Royal Bethlehem Asylum being the first hospital to benefit from the program and soon after the Royal Chelsea and Greenwich hospitals for disabled soldiers and sailors were established too. Private madhouses for the mentally distressed were also established. However, support for PWDs in terms of food, money and/or kind remained as an individual's Christian and civic duty, not the duty of the state. The church might provide some relief, but only for the destitute and disabled.

By the end of the 18th century, according to the Historic England (2020), “[I]n a population of around nine million people ... probably fewer than 10,000 lived in an institution” (para.10). However, the idea was growing that an institution was the most suitable place for people who are different. New specialist facilities were established on a belief that the disabled and the mentally ill could thrive in healthy, clean institutions. Life for many PWDs was about to change for the better indeed. In addition, the charity school movement (see Jones, 1938/2020, for detail) – based on a belief in civic order and progress – for the education of children from poor families also led to the founding of the first specialist schools for the deaf-and-dumb as well as the blind children. One good example is the Norwich School for Poor Boys (also known as the Anguish School) was established in 1617.

2.4 Fourth Disability Period: 1914-1945 AD (The Era of the Two World Wars)

The period of 1914-1945 is the era when two world wars were fought. The First World War (1914–18) was fought between the Central Powers (Germany and Austria-Hungary, joined later by Turkey and Bulgaria) and the alliance of Britain and its dominions (France, Russia, and others, joined later by Italy and the US). The Second World War (1939-1945) was a global war in which the vast majority of the countries, including all the great powers, eventually formed two opposing military alliances, i.e., the Allies (France, Poland and the United Kingdom, and their respective dependent states, e.g., British India; joined later by the independent Dominions of the British Commonwealth, i.e., Australia, Canada, New Zealand and South Africa; the United States joined in December 1941 after the Japanese attacked its Pearl Harbor; China officially joined the Allies in 1941) and the Axis (Germany, Italy and Japan).

During the First World War, as many as two million disabled British soldiers returned home from the battlefronts. The public attitude began to change, welcoming them back as national heroes who had sacrificed themselves mentally due to battle scars and bodily to injuries sustained during the fighting. As a result, life for PWDs was about to change again with major advances made in the following areas as listed by the Historic England (2020) below:

- (1) Plastic surgery and prosthetics;
- (2) Treatment approaches with new exercise and fitness were used with ex-servicemen who had sustained physical and mental damage;
- (3) Provision of sheltered or supported employment, e.g., the British Legion poppy factory in south London; and
- (4) New housing scheme ranging from single cottages to special villages (also known as self-contained colonies or villas) specially built for the PWDs who were mainly the disabled ex-servicemen. Each villa could house up to 60 PWDs, male and female as well as children. In each villa, there were “farms, laundries, bakeries, recreation halls, chapels and mortuaries ... and [S]egregation by sex, age and ability was strict” (Historic England, 2020, para. 7). However, the PWDs were isolated from the outside world.

One interesting event that took place during the era of the two world wars is the concept of eugenics – the so-called science of improving the humankind – that became a movement prevalent in the late 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. The ultimate goal of eugenics was “to eliminate human physical and mental defects altogether, in order to build a stronger society” (Historic England, 2020, para. 6). Many public figures including evolutionists and atheists agreed with the idea of eugenics. They believed that anyone, who was functionally disabled, mentally and/or physiologically defective, could become a liability or threat to the economic well-being of a country. Hence, the PWDs would be segregated from everyone else in the name of perfecting the human race.

Based on the writings (e.g., Galton, 1907, 1909) of Sir Francis Galton (b.1822-d.1911) on eugenics (see Gillham, 2001, for detail), eugenicists advocated for the sterilisation or even euthanasia of PWDs as well as those with mental illness or moral degeneration in order to prevent racial deterioration caused by what was believed to be degeneration in the genetic inheritance. In 1930, Sir Julian Sorell Huxley (b.1887-d.1975), who was the secretary of the London Zoological Society and also the co-founding chairman of the Eugenics Society, asked plaintively: “What are we going to do? Every defective man, woman and child is a burden. Every defective is an extra body for the nation to feed and clothe, but produces little or nothing in return” (cited in Unwin, 2020, para. 6).

Not forgetting, too, between 1900 and 1945, more than half a million of children in England suffered physical disability and/or sensory impairment as a result of poverty and disease. The families of these children came mainly from the working class and many were unable to afford high cost of specialist treatment or vaccinations for them. However, there were special schools (also known as open air schools and sunshine homes) set up for children who were crippled, blind and deaf, and/or in poor health. These children with disabilities “were trained for low-skilled work, but most people thought they would never find a job” (Historic England, 2020, para. 9).

2.5 Fifth Disability Period: since 1945 (Post-World War II Era)

With the Second World War ended in 1945, many stories of horror emerged, such as the mass killing of Jews in concentration camps throughout Europe, the euthanization of PWDs in Germany, and the unethical experiments carried out on innocent civilians and prisoners-of-war by the Japanese invaders in the Asia-Pacific region. As a result, the theories of eugenics that had been arguing for the isolation and sterilization of PWDs became increasingly reviled (Historic England, 2020).

With several hundred thousand ex-servicemen and women and civilians left disabled by the war, there was a public concern for these PWDs. The British government began to provide rehabilitation for all including workers who were disabled by industrial accidents. “The 1944 Disability Employment Act promised sheltered employment, reserved occupations and employment quotas for PWDs. Initiatives to restore the fitness, mobility, daily living skills and morale of disabled servicemen and women spread to the rest of the disabled population” (Historic England, 2020, para. 5-6).

The PWDs did not choose to remain passive or silent. Many campaigning disability charities were formed during the decades of 1940s and 50s. “A new social movement was started by a silent reproach march of disabled ex-servicemen in 1951. In the 1960s and 70s, the civil rights movement in the United States inspired groups of PWDs to take direct action against discrimination, poor access and inequality” (Historic England, 2020, para. 7-8). This is a social rather than medical model of PWDs (see Section 3 of this paper), and it was more concerned with rights of PWDs as members of the society. The issue of accessibility in terms of the barrier-free environment and job opportunities was of paramount importance to them. The PWDs have to make various adaptations to their living and working environments in order to be properly included. The pioneering work of Selwyn Goldsmith (b.1932-d.2011), author of *Designing for the Disabled* (1963), introduced the concept of free accessibility for PWDs. Soon architects and product designers took on the idea to design separate facilities for PWDs as well as to create buildings and landscapes which everyone with or without disability could use. It was Ronald Lawrence Mace (b.1941-d.1998), an American architect and product designer, who coined the term Universal Design (UD), which emerged from the barrier-free concepts, the broader accessibility movement, and the adaptive/assistive technology, in seeking to blend aesthetics into these three core considerations. In short, the concept of UD refers to the design of buildings, products or environments to make them accessible to all people, regardless of age, disability or other factors.

Another interesting event that took place during the early post-World War II was the birth of the Paralympic Games from a pioneering rehabilitation method in Stoke Mandeville Hospital in Aylesbury in 1948. The Games are now the second biggest sporting event in the world today. Many of the elite disabled athletes have become inspiring sporting icons in their own right.

Perhaps one uneventful episode during this era is the final closedown of the asylum which had involved many scandals related to neglect and abuse. With the Alexis Jay Report (Jay, 2014) into the sexual exploitation of children in Rotherham (1997-2013), the Communities and Local Government Committee called on the senior officers at Rotherham Council to Westminster to account for the management failures that allowed this abuse to go unchallenged for years (also see John Jay College of Criminal Justice, 2004, on the nature and scope of sexual abuse of minors by Catholic priests and deacons in the United States 1950-2002). As a result, a community care program for PWDs, especially those with learning disabilities and mental health needs, came into existence with tens of thousands of people leaving the long-term hospitals and returning to mainstream communities.

3. Models of People with Disabilities (M-PWDs)

There are several known Models of People With Disabilities (M-PWDs for short) published in the current literature of disability studies and five of them have been selected for a brief discussion in this paper: (a) the Religious model; (b) the Medical model; (c) the Social model; (d) the Rights-based model; and (e) the Media model. Each of these five models has led to several misconceptions about disability with unfair and unjust treatment of PWDs and the stereotypes associated with them. However, it is not within the scope of this paper to delve into the issue.

3.1 The Religious M-PWDs

The communities in the West (i.e., Europe and the Americas) are originally rooted in the Judea-Christian tradition, which often make claims that the roots of understanding bodily differences are referenced in the Bible. In the pre-21st century, ideas and thoughts about disabilities involved two possible explanations: In the first explanation, the view that PWDs were the result of evil spirits and the devil, or they were works of witchcraft or the subject of God's displeasure. It also included that these people were being punished as such for the sin of their parents or ancestors. This is indeed a very negative portrayal of PWDs. In the second explanation, the view offered is very different. It reflected the PWDs as the Suffering Christ and portrayed them to be angelic or of beyond-human status. While this second perspective is considerably kinder, the first perspective often leads to the formation of themes, such as sin, undesirability, bondage to the devil, burden and weakness around different communities of PWDs.

These religious stereotypes of PWDs created many misconceptions around the causes of disabilities. However, many changes have taken place in the new millennium as a result of these so-called traditional religious values and beliefs being challenged by the emergence of reason and rationality. In addition, legislations and laws have also been introduced and enacted against discrimination in many developed and developing countries throughout the world today.

3.2 The Medical M-PWDs

The pre-21st century Medical M-PWDs had resulted in many instances of unkind discrimination as well as unfair and unjust treatment of PWDs. If human worth was determined by perceived work value, productivity and profitability, PWDs often struggled to work and many could not work, and therefore, they were treated as economic liabilities, and, not surprising, seen as unproductive and incapable. The Medical M-PWDs was closely tied to economy and personal functionality in terms of his/her ability or capacity, and a PWD was often assessed as incapacity or inability. Hence, PWDs in many developing countries and, more so in the Third World countries, continue to have little or no access to adequate resources and

opportunities to study or work. The reason is simple: the problem is the result of limited and narrow mindset concerning the complexity of the multi-faceted concept of disability.

With a change in the perspective of the Medical M-PWDs in the recent decades in the new millennium, institutions, activity daycare centers and community homes for PWDs have been created with the triple-purpose of placement and/or provision of care services: Firstly, family members could go to work while their loved ones with disabilities are being taken care and provided for; secondly, such centers can provide respite for the family members who have to attend to PWDs 24/7; and thirdly, it can also become a training center where PWDs could become skilled and productive members of the community.

Given the right opportunity for PWDs to develop useful vocational skills, care for them can take a turn for the better, become less politicized and more professionalized. Also, the full-time staff working at those institutions or centers that provide day care and help services for PWDs will be properly trained, better equipped and licensed as professional practitioners. It should focus on advising, assisting and skilling people – both PWDs and full-time working staff – as well as treating them with respect as productive members of the community and not dismissed as an economic burden.

Unlike the previous M-PWDs that defined a PWD as an affected person, the change in the Medical M-PWDs is that it saw disability as a medico-social problem that affects the whole society and not just of the individual. To change the negative mindset, proper rehabilitation was introduced in the Medical M-PWDs.

3.3 The Social M-PWDs

The history of the Social M-PWDs starts with the history of the disability rights movement – a global social movement (see Bell, 2014, for detail) to secure equal opportunity and equal rights for all PWDs (Bagenstos, 2009). For example, in 1975, the UK-based Union of the Physically Impaired Against Segregation (UPIAS, 1972-1990) (Baldwinson, 2019) claimed that “[I]n our view it is society which disables physically impaired people. Disability is something imposed on top of our impairments by the way we are unnecessarily isolated and excluded from full participation in society” (also see Long, 2014, pp.3-10, for detail). This became known as “the social interpretation, or social definition, of disability” (Fleischer & Frieda, 2009, p.9).

The Social M-PWDs identifies the systemic barriers, derogatory attitudes, and social exclusion (intentional or inadvertent) that have made it difficult or impossible for PWDs to attain their valued functioning or occupational functionality. This M-PWDs diverges from the Medical M-PWDs that relies heavily on the functional analysis of the body as a machine to be fixed when it is damaged (e.g., physical injuries) in order to function normally as before or to conform with normative values (Paley, 2002).

3.4 The Rights-based M-PWDs

During the decade of 1980's, several countries (e.g., Australia, Canada, New Zealand and the United Kingdom) began to enact legislation that embraced rights-based discourse instead of custodial discourse. Such jurisprudence and enactment sought to address the issues of social justice and discrimination. The implementation of statutes by passing the relevant bills on PWDs in the parliament embraced the shift from disability being seen as an issue of medical problem to being part of the community membership with equal opportunity and fair access to social activities (e.g., employment, education and recreation). There was a paradigm shift in

from dependence to independence as PWDs demanded to have their political voice heard and acknowledged.

With the disability activism movement taking place in the US as well as the UK, it helped to ensure that legislation passed and entitlements were made available to many PWDs. However, although the Rights-based M-PWDs has contributed to additional entitlements for PWDs, it has failed to change the way in which the concept of disability is constructed and perceived. The stigma of a PWD having inferior genes or being regarded as abnormal continues to go unchallenged and the idea of community acceptance of PWDs remains elusive.

The failure of the Rights-based M-PWDs to dismantle the negative concept of disability, which relies on the conceptual construction of what disability is about, in order to support its claims for rights and entitlements. In fact, the Rights-based M-PWDs was more like a political strategy or tool – a way of locking PWDs into some kind of an identity group with a negative connotation. Like any other human rights treaty (e.g., the UN Convention of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, which was enacted on 3 May 2008), the Rights-Based M-PWDs is a visionary model designed to transform society into a more just society, but, to use Theresia Degener³'s words, “its visions cannot be achieved over night. Human rights implementation is a process with several agents and many hurdles to overcome” (Degener, 2014, p.2).

3.4 The Media M-PWDs

According to the Media M-PWDS, the mass media continues “to enforce disability stereotypes portraying disabled individuals in a negative un-empowering way” (Pirs & Popovska, 2013, p.42). In other words, the influence of media through various media organizations and their employees, political agendas, the intended audience and current societal trends has significantly contributed to the discrimination of disabled people through the reinforcement of impairment. In fact, throughout the media history, its creation and underpinning use of disabled stereotypes, the negative influence of organizations or employees, the use of images and terminology in a negative light and the under-representation of disabled people in the media. Shakespeare (1999) has rightly pointed out about disability in movie or television program that "impairment is made the most important thing" (p. 164) and disabled characters are "objectified and distanced from the audience" (p. 164).

A 1991 study done by Paul Hunt (cited in Pirs and Popovska, 2013) “identified 10 stereotypes that the media use to portray disabled people: 10 stereotypes were identified that the media used to portray disabled people: the disabled person as pitiable or pathetic; an object of curiosity or violence; sinister or evil; the super cripple; as atmosphere; laughable; his/her own worst enemy; as a burden; non-sexual; and unable to participate in daily life” (Pirs & Popovska, 2013, p. 42).

PART II: The Biblical Perspective on Disability and People with Disabilities

In this second part of the paper, the author has provided a brief introduction to Christian perspective on disability and PWDs. It must be emphasized at this juncture that taking a Christian perspective does not necessarily mean a biblical perspective, and it is often subjected to different theological understandings and interpretations. This brings the readers back to the Religious M-PWDs which has been briefly discussed earlier in the first part. The focus of this second part is on two important concepts: first, the concept of *Imago Dei*, which “refers most

³ Theresia Degener, a member of the Committee for the UN Convention of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, 2011-2018.

fundamentally to two things: first, God's own self-actualization through humankind; and second, God's care for humankind" (Counterbalance Foundation, 1995, para. 2); and second, the concept of *Imitatio Christi*, which "is the practice of following the example of Jesus" (O'Collins & Farrugia, 2004, p. 115).

4. What the Bible says about Disability

Returning to the Religious M-PWDs discussed earlier, it may appear quite difficult to agree on what the Bible says about disability. In the first perspective, especially in the past and even in some superstitious communities today, disabilities in people are often taken to be caused by evil spirits and the devil, the result of works of witchcraft or the subject of God's displeasure and punishment for the sin committed by the parents or ancestors of PWDs. In the second perspective, however, PWDs were seen as the Suffering Christ and depicted as being angelic or of beyond-human status. As a result of the traditional biblical understanding and different theological perspectives on disability and PWDs, Eiesland (1994) has identified the following three key theological themes in what he has termed as the Disabling Theology (see pp. 73-74):

- (1) Conflation of disability and sin: This is based on the belief that disability is a form of punishment for wrongdoing and it mars the divine image (i.e., *Imago Dei*) in humans;
- (2) Disability is perceived as virtuous suffering: It is seen as a form of suffering that must be endured for the purification of sinful nature in order to become righteous, and acceptance of such pain for the sake of unquestioned obedience to God; and
- (3) Disability is regarded as a case of charity and the means for creating justice.

Often most, if not all, PWDs do not want sympathy or pity. All they ask or want is to be treated equally and fairly, to have the same opportunities that other people without disabilities have. Moreover, most PWDs do not want to be singled out or treated differently making them feel like social outcasts (Okobokeye, 2013). The biggest hurdles these PWDs encounter daily is the way other people see and interact with them (Finch, 2019) and, in this paper, how Christians view and treat them (Govig, 1982; Njoroge, 2001).

In the Old Testament of the Holy Bible⁴, there are those who speculate that God does not value PWDs, and apparently, He does not accept such imperfect or defective people to be in the spiritual leadership or priesthood, as mentioned in the book of Leviticus chapter 21, verses 17-23 (or Leviticus 21:17-23)⁵:

¹⁷ "Say to Aaron: 'For the generations to come none of your descendants who has a defect may come near to offer the food of his God.

¹⁸ No man who has any defect may come near: no man who is blind or lame, disfigured or deformed;

¹⁹ no man with a crippled foot or hand,

²⁰ or who is a hunchback or a dwarf, or who has any eye defect, or who has festering or running sores or damaged testicles.

²¹ No descendant of Aaron the priest who has any defect is to come near to present the food offerings to the LORD. He has a defect; he must not come near to offer the food of his God.

²² He may eat the most holy food of his God, as well as the holy food;

⁴ All biblical verses quoted in this paper are taken from the New International Version (NIV) of the Holy Bible, unless otherwise stated.

⁵ All subsequent biblical verses will be presented in this way: Name of the Book taken, Chapter and Verse(s) quoted.

²³ yet because of his defect, he must not go near the curtain or approach the altar, and so desecrate my sanctuary. I am the LORD, who makes them holy.’

However, this is an erroneous interpretation of God’s impartial love and compassion. In Leviticus 21:17-23, its strict concern here is about the Aaronic priesthood, formally established in the book of Leviticus chapter 8. The concept of priesthood (and for the principles of priesthood, read Leviticus chapters 8-10) “is not new to the Pentateuch, i.e., the first five books of the Old Testament” (Deffinbaugh, 2014, para. 5) in the Holy Bible. It was in Sinai that God designated only Aaron, of the tribe of Levi, and his sons to be Israel’s priests (see Exodus 28:1). The rest of the Levities were to assist Aaron in the work of the tabernacle and also to take care of its furnishings (see Numbers 3:5–10). In other words, the Aaronic priesthood – also known as the Levitical priesthood – strictly refers to the lineage of Aaron and his sons within the tribe of Levi; the remaining Levities were designated as Aaron’s assistants. The work of the priests involved the following tasks:

- (1) Offering the morning and evening sacrifices on behalf of the community of Israel (Exodus 29:38-44);
- (2) Tending the vessels of the Holy Place (i.e., lampstand, altar of incense and bread of the Presence) (Exodus 27:20-21, 30:7-8; Leviticus 24:5-9);
- (3) (a) Inspecting unclean persons, and (b) when warranted, declaring them clean (Leviticus 24:13-14); and
- (4) Teaching the Law and administering justice under the Law (Deuteronomy 17:8).

As a group, the Aaronic priests anticipated or foreshadowed the coming of the perfect, sinless High Priest who is Jesus Christ. As stated in the book of Hebrews 7:24-27 in the New Testament as follows:

²⁴ but because Jesus lives forever, he has a permanent priesthood.

²⁵ Therefore he is able to save completely those who come to God through him, because he always lives to intercede for them.

²⁶ Such a high priest truly meets our need – one who is holy, blameless, pure, set apart from sinners, exalted above the heavens.

²⁷ Unlike the other high priests, he does not need to offer sacrifices day after day, first for his own sins, and then for the sins of the people. He sacrificed for their sins once for all when he offered himself.

Only Jesus Christ fits the profile of the perfect High Priest and He came to the world to die for humankind. Hence, no longer is there a need for physically perfect priests. That is to say that “apart from the restriction on impaired priests participating in ceremonies that looked toward the future, priests with disabilities were still priests” (General Council of the Assemblies of God, 2000, p. 2) whose every need was taken care by the divine command: “He may eat the most holy food of his God, as well as the holy food” (Leviticus 21:22). According to the official statement issued by the General Council of the Assemblies of God (2000) addressing the PWDs, it states that “God imparts ability, and He knows about disability because He at least allows it. God could have said to Moses⁶ (see Exodus 4:11) what He later said to Paul: “My grace is sufficient for you, for My power is made perfect in weakness” (2 Corinthians 12: 9).

⁶ Moses gave God his excuses why he was not the person to lead the Israelites out of Egypt. “The LORD said to him, “Who gave human beings their mouths? Who makes them deaf or mute? Who gives them sight or makes them blind? Is it not I, the LORD?” (Exodus 4:11)

In the biblical times, PWDs were rarely fully-functioning members of society. Jesus' response to disability (e.g., Matthew 9:36, Mark 1:41) was often to be “filled with pity” (the phrase as used in Good News Translation/GNT) or “moved with compassion” (used in New International Version/NIV), and then He reached out to touch and heal them. For example, as described in the gospel according to Matthew 9:36 and 14:14 below:

NIV 9:36 But when he saw the multitudes, he was *moved with compassion* on them, because they fainted, and were scattered abroad, as sheep having no shepherd.

GNT 9:36 As he saw the crowds, his heart was *filled with pity* for them, because they were worried and helpless, like sheep without a shepherd.

NIV 14:14 And Jesus went forth, and saw a great multitude, and was *moved with compassion* toward them, and he healed their sick.

GNT 14:14 Jesus got out of the boat, and when he saw the large crowd, his heart was *filled with pity* for them, and he healed those who were ill.

Apparently, these verses support the Medical M-PWDs, where a disabled needing help came to seek some form of treatment. The varying manifestations of God’s tremendous healing power as Jehovah-Rapha (i.e., “God who heals” in Hebrew) can be found in the Holy Bible and here are four examples (Malu, 2020, para. 9): “sickness and infirmity (Psalm 41:3); healing from mental affliction (Jonah 2:5-7); spiritual fatigue (Psalm 23:3); emotional suffering (Psalm 147:3); and anxiety or worry (John 14:27).” Interestingly, Xie (2018) has also argued that the earliest record about autism is during the biblical times around 30-32 AD (see Mark 9:17-29) and Jesus explained to his disciples that healing for it “can come out only by prayer (and fasting)” (Mark 9:29). Xie and Chua (2020) have also delved deeper into what is perceived as clinical depression⁷ experienced by King David when his third son, Prince Absalom, led a rebellion against his reign. The authors described the king’s condition as a transition from a sense of helplessness to a sense of hopelessness (see Psalm 6:1-7). Only through the help of Jehovah-Rapha that the king was able to cope his emotional suffering.

God as the Healer (Jehovah-Rapha) can be found in the Old Testament (OT) as provided in following selected three examples:

- Psalm 103:2-3 (OT) – Praise the LORD, my soul, and forget not all His benefits – who *forgives all your sins* and *heals all your diseases*.
- Isaiah 30:26 (OT) – The moon will shine like the sun, and the sunlight will be seven times brighter, like the light of seven full days, when the LORD *binds up the bruises* of His people and *heals the wounds* He inflicted.
- Hosea 6:1 (OT) – Come, let us return to the LORD. He has torn us to pieces but He *will heal us*; He has injured us but He *will bind up our wounds*.

According to Kalu (2020), the prophet Isaiah of the OT foreshadowed the healing ministry of Jesus (see Isaiah 61:1) and it was also confirmed in the New Testament (NT) by the Apostle Matthew (see Matthew 8:17). In the NT, Jesus is known as the Great Physician (see Mark

⁷ Also known as major depressive disorder, it is “a mental disorder characterized by a persistently depressed mood and long-term loss of pleasure or interest in life, often with other symptoms such as disturbed sleep, feelings of guilt or inadequacy, and suicidal thoughts” (Oxford University Press, 2020).

2:17). Moreover, the four gospels in the NT have recorded several healing miracles that Jesus performed during His short three-year ministry on earth, as given in the following three examples:

- Matthew 8:1-4 (NT) – when Jesus healed a leper; in verse 3: Jesus reached out his hand and touched the man. “I am willing,” he said. “Be clean!” Immediately he was *cleansed of his leprosy*.
- Mark 2:5-12 (NT) – when Jesus forgave and healed a paralyzed man; in verse 5: When Jesus saw their faith, he said to the paralyzed man, “Son, your *sins are forgiven*.”
- John 11:41-44 (NT) – when Jesus raised Lazarus from the dead; in verses 43-44: Jesus called in a loud voice, “*Lazarus, come out!*” The *dead man came out*, his hands and feet wrapped with strips of linen, and a cloth around his face. Jesus said to them, “Take off the grave clothes and let him go.”

Kalu (2020) pointed out that the healing ministry of Jesus has incorporated the qualities that Jehovah-Rapha bestowed upon the Israelites of the OT, i.e., healing from physical ailment as well as spiritual healing through forgiveness (see James 5:14-16). Today, Christians call on Jehovah-Rapha to heal them of physical ailments as well as to provide redemption for sins. “Christians believe that through the cleansing power of the blood of the Great Physician, Jesus Christ, they can rise from their old sinful life as new creations in the eternal fellowship with God” (Kalu, 2020, para. 14). As highlighted by Morris (2008), the words of Jesus sum up neatly a positive perspective on disability: “I have come that they may have life, and have it to the full” (John 10:10).

5. Understanding People with Disabilities from the Concept of *Imago Dei*

According to Morris (2008), like all other human beings, PWDs also reflect the image of the Creator God, and that means in likeness, or similarity, to God (Christianity.com, 2020). The diverse disabilities of PWDs do not, in any way, distort God’s image any more than anyone else simply because their bodies or minds do not conform to what society has defined as normal. By acknowledging this reality, it serves to remind Christians that PWDs should be accorded a full status and not lesser of being human. In this regard, Morris (2008) argued that every PWD, in his/her uniqueness, deserves the respect and love shown to anyone or anything that bears the mark of the Creator, i.e., *Imago Dei*.

What is *Imago Dei*? The term comes from the Latin Bible and is translated to English as “image of God.” As a theological term, it is applied uniquely to humans, denoting the unique symbolical relationship between God and humanity. Its longer definition refers most fundamentally to two things: “first, God’s own self-actualization through humankind; and second, God’s care for humankind” (Counterbalance Foundation, 1995, para. 1). *Imago Dei* as “the metaphysical expression, associated uniquely to humans, which signifies the symbolical connection between God and humanity” (Christianity.com, 2020, para. 2). The phrase *Imago Dei* can trace its origin back to Genesis 1:26-27, as follows:

²⁶ Then God said, “Let us make mankind in our image, in our likeness, so that they may rule over the fish in the sea and the birds in the sky, over the livestock and all the wild animals,^[a] and over all the creatures that move along the ground.”

²⁷ So God created mankind in his own image, in the image of God he created them; male and female he created them.

The two verses from the book of Genesis do not imply that God is in human form, but that “humans are in the image of God in their moral, spiritual, and intellectual essence” (Counterbalance Foundation, 1995, para. 1). In other words, the humankind reflects the divine nature of the Creator God in their ability to achieve the unique characteristics with which they have been endowed, and such “qualities make humans different than all other creatures: rational structure, creative freedom, a possibility for self-actualization, and the ability for self-transcendence” (Christianity.com, 2020, para. 3).

According to Handoyo (2020a), the biblical fact that humans are created in God’s image should empower Christians in their understanding of themselves as well as PWDs in the following five ways: “Firstly, with the *Imago Dei* in us, we are higher than any other living creatures in this planet ... but we are created just a little lower than angels (see Psalm 8:5)” (para. 9). He further argued that “we should not degrade ourselves in our behaviour and morality. Animals do not have intellect and logic like us thus their behaviours are based on the instinct they have ... Human beings have the same instinct too but our logic can control our bodily instinct” (Handoyo 2020a, para. 10). Secondly, with the *Imago Dei*, Christians should never lose hope even when they encounter hurdles in their lives, such as difficulty, failure and rejection. With God’s image in them, they can overcome life’s challenges. Thirdly, with the *Imago Dei*, Christians “are given authority to subdue the world and to have dominion over all living creatures on this earth (see Genesis 1:28)” (Handoyo, 2020a, para. 13). That, of course, includes viruses with the current problematic coronavirus in the Covid-19 pandemic, which are considered as living things, which humankind will develop a vaccine to bring them under control soon. Fourthly, “with the *Imago Dei* in us, we should empower others who are marginalised and disadvantaged in the society and that includes people with disabilities. The reason is that regardless of their disabilities, they are also created in God’s image” (Handoyo, 2020a, para. 15). God uses the PWDs for His glory. He “allows some people to be disabled to show His awesome love for all of creation and to help us imitate His love” (Chery, 2020, para. 2). According to Chery (2020), “God uses the disabled to teach us things and to accomplish His purposes in our lives ... *for* His ways are higher than our ways” (para. 3). For instance, Nick Vuijic, a well-known Australian Christian evangelist and motivational speaker, was born with tetra-amelia syndrome (a rare disorder characterized by the absence of arms and legs) but God has used him mightily to inspire millions and to advance His Kingdom (see Vuijic. 2010, for detail). Many good people such as Mother Teresa, who ministered to “the hungry, of the naked, of the homeless, of the blind, of the lepers, of all those who feel unwanted, unloved, uncared for throughout society ... *for* most of her life” (Escobar, 2020, p. 30), have been called by God to cater as well as to empower those have been marginalised in the society. “Because of their dedication, those with intellectual disabilities, those who are destitute, the orphans, jobless and hopeless in the society have their dignity back as human beings who bear God’s image” (Handoyo, 2020a, para. 15). Finally, Handoyo (2020a) emphasized that “with the *Imago Dei* in us, let’s be a problem solver rather than a problem maker wherever we are ... *because* ... [P]roblems are inevitable in workplaces, at home, schools and anywhere” (para. 16).

The Christianity.com (2020) summed it up very nicely when it stated that for humans to be “in the image of God (with the *Imago Dei*) is to recognize the special qualities of human nature which allow God to be made manifest in humans ... to have the conscious recognition ... that they are the creature through whom God’s plans and purposes can be made known and actualized; humans, in this way, can be seen as co-creators with God.” (para. 3). The moral implications of the concept of *Imago Dei* are very obvious: if humans are to love God, then they must love other humans, as each is an expression of God. The human’s likeness to God is

best understood by contrasting it with what does not portray His divine image. Therefore, “[S]triving to bring about the *Imago Dei* in one's life can be seen as the quest for wholeness, or one's essential self, as pointed to in Christ's life and teachings” (Christianity.com, 2020, para. 3). This brings us to the next concept, that of *Imitatio Christi*, which will be elaborated in the next section below.

6. Understanding the People with Disabilities from the Concept of *Imitatio Christi*

Imitatio Christi (i.e., Imitation of Christ) refers to the attempt to live and act as Christ lived and acted during His 33 years on earth. The ideal of *Imitatio Christi* constitutes an important element of Christian theology, ethics and spirituality (Jestice, 2004; Richardson & Bowden, 1983). References to this concept and its practice are found in the earliest Christian documents, such as the Pauline Epistles (Jestice, 2004).

A Christian devotional book of the same title *The Imitation of Christ* written between 1390 and 1440 by Thomas à Kempis, “first composed in Latin as *De Imitatione Christi* (ca. 1418–1427)” (Miola, 2007, p. 285). Although its authorship is a matter of controversy, the author was a representative of the *devotio moderna* (*q.v.*) movement, of which Kempis was a member, and “its two offshoots, the Brethren of the Common Life and the Congregation of Windsheim” (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2020, para. 1). Interestingly, the text is divided into four books to provide detailed spiritual instructions: (1) Helpful Counsels of the Spiritual Life; (2) Directives for the Interior Life; (3) On Interior Consolation; and (4) On the Blessed Sacrament. The approach taken in the *Imitatio Christi* is characterized by the emphasis on the inner life as well as withdrawal from the world, as opposed to an active imitation of Christ by other friars (Espín & Nickoloff, 2007).

Handoyo (2020b) has argued that it not possible for Christians “to imitate Christ perfectly while we are living in this world due to the sinful nature which is inborn in us but to be like Him should be the goal of our lives” (para. 6). Jesus has demonstrated Himself during His earthly ministry how His followers should imitate Him with the help of the Holy Spirit. Handoyo (2020b) expounded the concept of *Imitatio Christi* in the following three points: First, Christians should imitate Jesus’ humility without the need to be an angel to be humble. “Humility is within our reach. Even those who do not have the Holy Spirit can humble themselves. How much more we are believers who have the Holy Spirit living in us, so we should be able to imitate Christ’s humility” (Handoyo, 2020b, para. 7). Apostle Paul has described Jesus’ humility perfectly as follows: “In your relationships with one another, have the same mindset as Christ Jesus, who, being in very nature God, did not consider equality with God something to be used to his own advantage; rather, he made himself nothing by taking the very nature of a servant, being made in human likeness” (Philippians 2:5-7). Practically, according to Handoyo (2020b), to be humble can be expressed in the way Christians treat others: consider others including PWDs more important than them (see Philippians 2:3), respect others (see Romans 12:10). “Being humble can also be in the form of willingness to acknowledge our mistakes ... instead of putting the blame on others when something bad happened because of our actions ... in the form of willingness to listen to others rather than others must listen to us (see James 1:19). The list can go on and on” (Handoyo, 2020b, para. 8). Second, Christians are encouraged to imitate Jesus’s obedience to His Father. Philippians 2:8 says, “And being found in appearance as a man, He humbled Himself by becoming obedient to death – even death on a cross!” Jesus’ obedience to the point of death on the cross, as explained by Handoyo (2020b), shows that Jesus has total obedience to His Father despite all authorities being given to Him (see Matthew 28:18), during His earthly ministry, with the exception that only His Father held the authority above Him and hence, Jesus humbly submitted

Himself to die on the cross. Third, Christians are reminded to imitate the love of Jesus and His compassion to all the people, including PWDs. As recorded in the four gospels in the NT, Jesus heals the sick, feeds the hungry, receives the marginalized, forgives the sinners, and finally, He gives His all to even those who reject Him. Handoyo (2020b) firmly stressed that “Jesus walks the talks; He practices what He preaches. His practical ministries are in line with His doctrinal teaching. Jesus shows His faith by His works” (para. 11). Apostle James elaborates what it means having faith with works (see James 2:14-17); “[I]n the same way, faith by itself, if it is not accompanied by action, is dead” (James 2:17).

Handoyo (2020b) has argued that the above list of examples of *Imitatio Christi* is still incomplete with many more to identify in terms of Jesus’ selfless examples that all can imitate (e.g., His gentleness). By putting *Imitatio Christi* into practice, others, especially the non-believers, may see Christ in His followers. What Jesus has demonstrated in terms of His selfless values during His ministry on earth are attainable with God’s empowerment through the work of the Holy Spirit. A Christian’s imitation of Christ is never perfect, yet even a little imitation can encourage others to come to know Him. God does not call His people to love Him only but also to love their neighbors and these include also PWDs and the less fortunate others (see Mark 12:30-31).

Conclusion

Between the concepts of *Imago Dei* and *Imitatio Christi*, there remains so much to be explored though it is not within the scope of this paper. There are two key underlying lessons to acquire from this paper. Firstly, *Imago Dei* is in all people, i.e., created in the image of God. Therefore, everyone possessed the intrinsic value, not based on what s/he can do or offer, but on who s/he is. Whether one is with or without disability, s/he remains as part of God’s divine creation. With the fall of Adam and Eve in the Garden of Eden caused by the sin of disobedience (see Genesis 3:1-24), the humankind has inevitably tarnished the image of God. The consequence was followed by suffering (e.g., sickness, disability, anxiety and depression, to name just a few) and eventually, death. This become the greatest weakness of humankind. However, Apostle Paul explained, “But He [Jesus] said to me, ‘My grace is sufficient for you, for My power is made perfect in weakness.’ Therefore, I will boast all the more gladly about my weaknesses, so that Christ’s power may rest on me. That is why, for Christ’s sake, I delight in weaknesses, in insults, in hardships, in persecutions, in difficulties. For when I am weak, then I am strong” (2 Corinthians 12:8-10). The last sentence is also echoed in Joel 3:10, “Let the weak say, ‘I am strong.’” Secondly, with Jesus’ earthly ministry to reach out to humankind and, more importantly, to redeem the world from the bondage and condemnation of sin, He has set the precedent for the Christians to abide by God’s calling to do within their own means and in *Imitatio Christi*: “Do not withhold good from those to whom it is due, when it is in your power to act” (Proverbs 3:27). The calling to Christians – “[F]or *they* are God’s handiwork, created in Christ Jesus to do good works, which God prepared in advance for *them* to do” (Ephesians 2:10) – to play the role of disability advocates is to carry on Jesus’ work so that all people, especially PWDs, will experience the warm welcome to the body of Christ and be encouraged to use their gifts in His ministry (DeYoung & Stephenson, 2009).

References

1. Bagenstos, S. (2009). Law and the contradictions of the disability rights movement. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
2. Behring Center, National Museum of American History (2015). Disability history. Retrieved from: <https://americanhistory.si.edu/topics/disability-history>

3. Bell, B. (2014, 5 August). The global disability rights movement: Winning power, participation, and access. Huffington Post. Retrieved from: https://www.huffpost.com/entry/the-global-disability-rig_b_5651235?guccounter=1&guce_referrer=aHR0cHM6Ly9lbi53aWtpcGVkaWEub3JnLw&guce_referrer_sig=AQAAACmy_h5tjm1VCSX1719oOOROq2max_NYpQszjneFI1Jn7H8iyqOdfn1z7i5o6ep7uOu8EnCb604isoLi_1-J6ZBHKg6hv7K05731bsGYMDCIGIFovP40x1Mee47NBIHWv0sxECDfyCupQAavbW1eHqNLUvQ8qQ3LtsfNAXq9HT7.
4. Baldwinson, T. (2019). UPIAS: The Union of the Physically Impaired Against Segregation (1972-1990): A public record from private files. TBR Imprint.
5. Brown, S. (2015). United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Disabled Persons. Encyclopedia Britannica Incorporated, Chicago, IL, USA. Retrieved from: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/United-Nations-Declaration-on-the-Rights-of-Disabled-Persons>.
6. Carrel, A. (1939). Man, the unknown. New York, NY: Harper & Brothers.
7. Changes in the Views of Disability (n.d.). Models of disability. Retrieved from: <https://sites.google.com/site/changesintheviewsofdisability/models-of-disability>.
8. Changes in the Views of Disability (n.d.). Treatment of disabled people throughout history. Retrieved from: <https://sites.google.com/site/changesintheviewsofdisability/treatment-of-disabled-people-throughout-history>.
9. Chery, F. (2020, 15 July). Bible reasons: Disabilities. Retrieved from: <https://biblereasons.com/disabilities/>
10. Christianity.com (2020). What does "Imago Dei" mean? The image of God in the Bible. Retrieved from: <https://www.christianity.com/wiki/bible/image-of-god-meaning-imago-dei-in-the-bible.html>.
11. Clapton, J., & Fitzgerald, J. (2005). The history of disability: A history of 'otherness'. New Renaissance Magazine. Retrieved from: <http://www.ru.org/human-rights/the-history-of-disability-a-history-of-otherness.html>.
12. Counterbalance Foundation (1995). Glossary definitions: Imago dei. Retrieved from: <https://www.pbs.org/faithandreason/theogloss/imago-body.html>.
13. Deffinbaugh, B. (2014, 18 May). Principles of Priesthood (Leviticus 8-10). Retrieved from: <https://bible.org/seriespage/7-principles-priesthood-leviticus-8-10>
14. Degener, T. (2014). A human rights model of disability. Bochum, Germany: Evangelische Fachhochschule Rheinland-Westfalen-Lippe
15. DeYoung, T.A., & Stephenson, M. (2009). Everybody belongs. Everybody serves: A handbook for disability advocates. Grand Rapids, MI: Disability Concerns

16. Eiesland, N.L. (1994). *The disabled God: Toward a liberatory theology of disability*. Nashville, TN: Abington Press.
17. Escobar, E.P. (2020, 30 July). Touch the needy. In *Our Daily Bread* (June, July and August issue). Our Daily Bread Ministries. Retrieved from: <https://odb.org/2020/07/30/touch-the-needy>
18. Espín, O.O., & Nickoloff, J.B. (Eds.). (2007). *An introductory dictionary of theology and religious studies*. Collegeville, MN: Liturgical Press.
19. Finch, C. (2019, 28 November). What people with disabilities want the public and the media to know. *You Me Mind Body*. Retrieved from: <https://youmemindbody.com/disabilities/What-People-with-Disabilities-Want-the-Public-and-the-Media-to-Know>
20. Fleischer, D.Z., & Frieda, Z. (2001). *The disability rights movement: From charity to confrontation*. Philadelphia, PA: Temple University Press.
21. Galton, F. (1907). *Probability, the foundation of eugenics*. The Herbert Spencer Lecture. Oxford, UK: Clarendon Press.
22. Galton, F. (1909). *Essays in eugenics*. London, UK: Eugenics Education Society.
23. General Council of the Assemblies of God (2000). *Ministry to people with disabilities: A biblical perspective*. The statement on ministry to people with disabilities adopted by the General Presbytery of the Assemblies of God, August 11. Springfield, MO: The Author.
24. Gillham, N.W. (2001). *A life of Sir Francis Galton: From African exploration to the birth of Eugenics*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
25. Goldsmith, Selwyn (1963). *Designing for the disabled: a manual of technical information*. London, UK: Royal Institute of British Architects.
26. Govig, S. (1982). Disabled persons in the congregation: Toward a theology of encouragement. *African Theological Journal*, 11, 85-102.
27. Handoyo, T.S. (2020a). *Devotion: Imago Dei*. Whatsapp Devotion Series, 20 July.
28. Handoyo, T.S. (2020b). *Devotion: Imitatio Christi*. Whatsapp Devotion Series, 27 July.
29. Historic England (2020). *A history of disability: From 1050 to the present day*. Retrieved from: <https://historicengland.org.uk/research/inclusive-heritage/disability-history/>
30. Howell, M., & Ford, P. (1980/1992). *The true history of the elephant man* (3rd ed.). London, UK: Penguin Books.
31. Jay, A. (2014). *An independent inquiry into child sexual exploitation in Rotherham (1997-2013)*. Retrieved from: <https://www.rotherham.gov.uk/downloads/file/279/independent-inquiry-into-child-sexual-exploitation-in-rotherham>.
32. Jestice, P.G. (Ed.). (2004). *Holy people of the world: a cross-cultural encyclopedia* (Vol. 3). Santa Barbara, CA: ABC-CLIO.
33. John Jay College of Criminal Justice (2004). *Executive Summary: The nature and scope of sexual abuse of minors by Catholic priests and deacons in the United States 1950-2002*. United States Conference of Catholic Bishops. Retrieved from: <http://www.usccb.org/issues-and-action/child-and-youth-protection/upload/The-Nature-and-Scope-of-Sexual-Abuse-of-Minors-by-Catholic-Priests-and-Deacons-in-the-United-States-1950-2002.pdf>
34. Jones, M.G. (1938/2020). *The charity school movement: A study of eighteenth century Puritanism in action*. London, UK: Routledge.
35. Kalu, M. (2020). *What Does it Mean That God Is Jehovah-Rapha?* Retrieved from: <https://www.christianity.com/wiki/god/what-does-it-mean-that-god-is-jehovah-rapha.html>
36. Long, A. (2014). *Reasonable accommodation as professional responsibility, reasonable accommodation as professionalism*. Davis, CA: University of California.
37. Miola, R.S. (2007). *Early modern Catholicism: An anthology of primary sources*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.

38. Morris, W. (2008). *Theology without words: Theology in the deaf community – explorations in practical, pastoral and empirical theology*. New York, NY: Routledge
39. National Council on Disability (1978/2020). National Council on Disability. Retrieved from: <https://ncd.gov/about>.
40. Njoroge, N. (2001). Not an option: Ministry with and for persons with disabilities. *Ministerial Formation*, 92, 5-8.
41. O'Collins, G., & Farrugia, E.G. (2004). *A concise dictionary of theology*. New York, NY: Paulist Press.
42. Okobokeyeime, H. (2013, 12 October). People with disabilities as social outcasts: Shifting the perspective from victim to advocate. *The Huffington Post*. Retrieved from: https://www.huffpost.com/entry/people-with-disabilities-1_b_3744152
43. Oxford Dictionaries online (2020). *Clinical depression*. Oxford, UK; Oxford University Press.
44. Paley, J. (2002). The Cartesian melodrama in nursing. *Nursing Philosophy*, 3(3), 189-192.
45. Pirs, D., and Popovska, S. (2013). Media mediated disability: How to avoid stereotypes. *International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Research*, 1(4), 42-45.
46. Richardson, A., & Bowden, J. (Eds.) (1983). *The Westminster dictionary of Christian theology*. Westminster, UK: John Knox Press.
47. Shakespeare, T. (1999). Art and lies? Representations of disability on film. In Corker, M. & French, S. (Eds.), *Disability discourse* (pp. 164-172). Buckingham, UK: Open University Press.
48. Unwin, S. (2020, 17 February). Eugenics and the intellectuals. *Byline Times*. Retrieved from: <https://bylinetimes.com/2020/02/17/eugenics-and-the-intellectuals/>
49. Vujicic, N. (2010). *A life of value: Life without limits*. New York, NY: Doubleday Books.
50. Xie, G.H. (2018). The spectral symptoms of autism: The scriptural-nosographical narrative from the Christian perspective. *World Wide Journal of Multi-disciplinary Research and Development*, 4(8), 25-37.
51. Xie, G.H., & Chua, J.S. (2020). King David as an optimally developed person in the sense of helplessness and hopelessness. *World Wide Journal of Multi-disciplinary Research and Development*, 6(6), 38-43.